

INFLUENCE OF THE FLEXOGRAPHIC PRINTING PROCESS PARAMETERS AND MATERIAL PROPERTIES ON PRINT QUALITY

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Abstract: *Flexographic printing is a printing technique that, like all the other printing techniques, depends on a number of parameters defining the process and the final product quality. Flexographic print quality is also influenced by the nature of various materials and their parameters. Process and material parameters influencing the printed product quality are present in all of the production phases. This paper aims to conduct a literature review regarding the most important process parameters and properties of the materials present in the printing phase, as well as the level of their influence on the print quality parameters. The focus of the review is on the anilox rollers, printing pressure, printing speed, and ink viscosity. The anilox roller or anilox sleeve choice has a significant impact on print quality mainly through the achieved density and tonal value increase. The most important anilox roller parameters are screen ruling, capacity, cell shape, cell depth, cell wall thickness, cell depth to width ratio, angle of the cell walls. On the other hand, the combined influence of the pressure setting and printing speed is the critical point of the flexographic printing process if the aim is to obtain regular halftone dots, avoid the halo effect and control the tonal value increase. All of the aforementioned parameters can yield different print quality results depending on the ink viscosity, making it another critical factor to be investigated. Apart from that, ink viscosity itself can be greatly influenced by the printing speed and temperatures, which are developing mainly on the anilox roller surface. The literature review in this paper should help enable further research regarding*

the influence of other scarcely investigated materials in the flexographic printing process, such as printing sleeves, on the print quality, as well as the mechanisms of their interaction with other materials during the printing.

Keywords: flexography, pressure, printing speed, anilox, viscosity

1 INTRODUCTION

Flexographic printing is a printing technique that, like all the other printing techniques, depends on a number of parameters defining the process and the final product quality. Flexographic print quality is also influenced by the nature of various materials and their parameters. Process and material parameters influencing the printed product quality are present in all of the production phases, especially the printing phase. The literature review on some of the parameters present in the printing process should help enable further research regarding the influence of other scarcely investigated materials in the flexographic printing process on print quality and other process parameters.

2 INFLUENCE OF THE FLEXOGRAPHIC PRINTING PROCESS PARAMETERS AND MATERIAL PROPERTIES ON PRINT QUALITY

2.1 Printing speed and pressure

Pressure adjustment is a critical point of the flexographic printing process if the aim is to achieve finely shaped halftone dots, prevent the occurrence of halo effects and control the tonal value increase. The printing substrate moves between the plate cylinder and the impression cylinder, and the distance between them, i.e., the printing NIP, must be optimal in order to achieve the optimal printing pressure (FTA, 2003). Ideally, the printing pressure in flexography is very low (Kiss Print). Kiss Print is the minimum pressure of the printing plate on the substrate required to print a clear image (about 0.1016 mm of contact depth of the materials in the printing NIP) (Bould et al., 2004). Many innovations in flexography are directed towards achieving controlled pressures in the printing press (Johnson, 2003).

Ink transfer to the substrate is one of the key parameters in the flexographic printing process (Johnson et al., 2004). As the printing form is flexible, the logical consequence of the increased pressure is the deformation of the geometry of the halftone dots, which acquire an elliptical shape instead of a circular one. Halftone elements on standard digital printing plates were rendered very sensitive to pressure changes in the study performed by

(Hamblyn, 2015) and caused a more significant tonal value increase. Numerical modeling of halftone elements without the ink shows that the flatter their top, the more uniform the pressure distribution on their surface, as well as deeper inside the photopolymer, thus reducing the share of deformation of the side walls. According to (Borbély & Szentgyörgyvölgyi, 2011), the densitometric values most affected by pressure variations are tonal values, halftone dot shape and tonal gradations.

If the pressure is too low, details in the highlight areas may not be transferred properly to the substrate. Higher pressure values, in contrast, can lead to ink smearing around the edges of printed areas. The higher the pressure, the more susceptible the halftone elements are to deformation and squeezing the color out, which results in tonal value increase (Boonprasit, 2006).

Studies of the influence of printing pressure on OPP material have proven that the pressure between the printing plate and the impression cylinder has the greatest impact on the reproduction of halftones with a significant increase in optical density (Bohan et al., 2003; Du, 2009). The increase in pressure in this zone significantly affects the mechanical deformations of the printing elements, where halftone elements with a round top show less consistent results and greater sensitivity to changes in the pressure than elements with a flat top.

(Valdec, Zjakić & Milković, 2013) concluded that with increasing pressure, the tonal value increase in the case of printing plates with round top halftone elements is more pronounced than the tonal value increase for printing plates with flat top halftone elements (12% tonal value increase for 40% TV for round tops at 380 lines/cm screen ruling and 4% under the same conditions for flat tops). Also, in their research, they noted that the largest tonal value increase occurs in areas with coverage of less than 3% due to the collapse of halftone elements. They immersed themselves in the cells of the anilox roller, thus taking on the excess ink. In the case of round top elements, the spreading of the ink on the substrate significantly affected the size of the printed halftone dot, due to the fact that the pressure is stronger in the middle of the halftone element, leading to ink squeezing out and producing the so-called halo-effect.

The results of research conducted by (Valdec, Miljković & Čerepinko, 2018) showed that with increasing pressure, the thickness of the ink layer on the substrate decreases. This was the main reason for the non-uniformity of the optical density on the surface of the halftone dot printed using round top dot printing plates. In the middle of the halftone dot, there was a decrease in the thickness of the ink, in contrast to the accumulation of the ink on the edges, causing tonal value increase.

(Bould, Claypole & Bohan, 2003) examined the effect of pressure on print quality at three different screen ruling. The mechanical tonal value increase was the greatest at the highest pressure and screen ruling. The pressure had a greater effect on the tonal value increase than the screen ruling.

(Hannah, 1951) investigated the contact between hard and soft rollers in a printing NIP, concluding that the pressure profile is most affected by the thickness of the compressible elastomer layer and the contact area width.

(Bould, Claypole & Bohan, 2004) state that the tonal value increase becomes more significant with increasing pressure and that this phenomenon is more pronounced in highlight areas after each increase in pressure, while in the case of shadow areas, it is not. This led the authors to the conclusion that in highlight areas, both main mechanisms of mechanical deformation of halftone elements occur, while in the case of shadows, only one of them is present. The authors also state that the pressure in flexographic printing has the greatest influence on the tonal value increase and that it occurs more due to the ink spreading than the deformation of the printing plate elements. An increase in printing speed leads to a less pronounced tonal value increase since the ink does not have enough time to spread in the printing NIP zone.

(Olsson et al., 2006) observed during the study that halftone dots have a larger diameter in the printing direction than in the transverse direction. At low pressures, the dots become narrower in the transverse direction, which is most likely a consequence of the combined influence of the movement of the substrate through the printing NIP and the simultaneous pressing of the substrate with the printing plate, which leads to the deformation of halftone elements. (Lagerstedt & Kolseth, 1995) made a similar observation in their research. Namely, with the pressure increase, there was a significant stretching and even merging of the halftone dots in the printing direction.

(Johnson et al., 2003) have experimentally shown that ink transfer increases with increasing pressure and decreases with increasing speed. In addition, they found that ink transfer differed between softer and harder printing plates, although it was concluded that the main deformations occur in the compressible layer of the sleeve. They explained this by the greater ability of the softer printing plate to adapt to the surface of the printing substrate, thus increasing the contact area.

However, some researchers characterize the effect of pressure differently. (Bohan et al., 2003) state that the influence of pressure in the printing NIP is less significant than the influence of pressure in other contact zones in the printing press. Namely, increasing the pressure between the ink chamber and

the anilox roller improves the ink transfer. This is explained by the effect of the load on the doctor blades, which changes their contact angle on the anilox roller. Their research also noted a decrease in ink transfer with increasing pressure between the printing plate and the anilox roller. However, no more detailed explanation of this phenomenon was given.

The pressure between the printing plate and the printing substrate affects the roughness of the porous substrates. Higher pressure forces compress the fiber network and align them, thus increasing the ink and substrate contact surface. The increase in pressure also leads to the lateral flowing of ink on the surface and, in the case of porous substrates to its penetration into the substrate through capillary sorption (Fetsko & Walker, 1955; Walker & Fetsko, 1955; De Grâce & Mangin, 1983; Johnson et al., 2003; Hamblyn, 2004; Beynon, 2007; Bould et al., 2011).

(Schaeffer, Fisch & Zettlemyer, 1963) concluded that the ink transfer improves with an increase in speed and pressure. Studying the ink transfer dependence on the properties of the substrate and printing conditions, (De Grâce & Mangin, 1983) found that increasing the pressure leads to a larger amount of ink being pushed into the substrate (newsprint). However, they also concluded that if the pressure is too large, individual pores close, thus leading to decreased ink transfer.

(Schaeffer, Fisch & Zettlemyer, 1963) also observed that at low printing speeds, higher pressure forces negatively affect pore diameters. Due to the longer time that the substrate spends in the printing NIP at low printing speeds, the pressure forces deform it easier, closing its pores and thus reducing the ink transfer due to the reduced ability of vehicle absorption.

As the print speed increases, the time the substrate spends in the printing NIP (typically measured in milliseconds) decreases. As the ink is pushed into the substrate pores in the printing NIP, a decrease in this time leads to a decrease in ink transfer as well (Fetsko & Walker, 1955; Walker & Fetsko, 1955; De Grâce & Mangin, 1983; Zang, 1992; Damroth et al., 1996; Fouche & Blayo, 2001; Johnson et al., 2003; Hamblyn, 2004). Contrary to this observation, (Quinn et al., 1997) and (Olsson et al., 2007) observed an increase in ink transfer with increasing print speed. This is explained by the fact that by spending less time in the printing NIP, the substrate is less compressed, which leaves its pores open to accept a larger amount of ink.

In many studies, an increase in optical density has been observed along with an increase in pressure in the range of lower values. In a study of the impact of pressure on print quality on foil, (Borbély & Szentgyörgyvölgyi, 2011) concluded

that optical density does not increase with pressure. However, in the range of higher values, the increase in optical density is initially less pronounced and then reaches a maximum value (Mirle, 1989; Johnson et al., 2003; Hamblyn, 2004; Holmvall & Uesaka, 2008). (Fetsko & Walker, 1955) investigated the effect of pressure on the printing process and concluded that the percentage of ink transferred from the printing plate increases with increasing pressure, and (Bould et al., 2004) concluded that at high pressures, the growth in ink transfer stops after one moment. (Olsson et al., 2006) state that the highest values of optical density are achieved at medium pressure values.

A large number of authors in their research concluded that increasing the pressure in the printing NIP also improves ink transfer and that a large number of different mechanisms contribute to this (Bohan et al., 2003; Johnson et al., 2003; Hamblyn, 2004; Beynon, 2007; Cherry, 2007; Holmvall & Uesaka, 2008). At higher pressures, the contact zone between the printing plate and the substrate increases. In addition, in porous, incompressible substrates, the amount of ink immobilized ink pushed into the substrate increases, thus achieving less dependence on the ratio of ink amount transferred to the substrate and the amount remaining on the printing plate after separation.

Increasing the pressure contributes to achieving more uniform prints in several ways. Increasing the contact area reduces the proportion of unprinted parts of the substrate on the final print. Lateral ink flowing and the tendency of achieving a closed ink film are also growing.

However, as the change in pressure affects the ink separation process, problems can occur in the form of various repetitive motifs, primarily with water-based inks.

2.2 Anilox rollers

The choice of anilox rollers significantly affects the print quality through the achieved optical density and the tonal value increase.

The amount of transferred ink depends on the properties of the anilox rollers or sleeves and the rheological properties of the ink. The most important parameters of anilox rollers that can affect the print quality are ruling (line/cm), which determines the number of cells on the surface of the roller or sleeve, capacity (cm^3/m^2), shape, depth, openness (width), cell wall thickness, the ratio of the depth and width of the cells, the angle of the inner walls of the cells, the surface properties of the anilox rollers (depending on the properties of the material used for coating).

The range of line ruling for anilox roller most commonly used in printing processes is from 80 to 500 lines/cm (Dunn, 2015; FFTA, 2014). If an anilox roller or a sleeve with low line ruling and higher capacity were chosen for fine detail printing, the tonal value increase would be too pronounced, rendering highlights almost impossible to reproduce. Too high of a line ruling would, in contrast, lead to reduced ink transfer and optical density.

Capacity is a property used to determine the amount of ink that an anilox roller or sleeve transfers to a printing plate. It is important to note that the cells of the anilox rollers never empty to the bottom during ink transfer and that they retain between 40% and 60% of the ink they carry. The most commonly used anilox rollers have a capacity of 0.95 to 13.5 cm³/m² (FFTA, 2014). An increase in the capacity of the anilox roller leads to an increase in optical density due to an increase in the amount of ink available for transferring. However, it also leads to a greater tonal value increase (Damroth et al., 1996; Lindholm et al., 1996; Fouche & Blayo, 2001; Hamblyn, 2004; Beynon, 2007; Bould et al., 2011).

The ink transfer between the anilox roller and the printing plate is also determined by the geometry of the cells themselves (Hamblyn, 2004; Cherry, 2007; Bould et al., 2011), where smaller cells provide greater resistance to ink extraction. Today, the most commonly used cell geometry implies a hexagonal cross-sectional shape (like a honeycomb). The cell diameter is another parameter that affects the print quality, and it directly depends on the line ruling. It is important that it be smaller than the diameter of the smallest printing element on the printing plate; otherwise, the printing elements will be immersed in the cells. This would further lead to the ink being transferred to the surface and the sidewalls of printing elements, contributing to the tonal value increase as time passes (Laden, 1997).

The surface properties of the material used for anilox roller coating also affect the amount and uniformity of ink transfer. The most commonly used ceramic-coated anilox rollers should have a surface porosity of less than 1%, uniform coating application and high surface tension (Izdebska, 2016).

2. 3 Ink viscosity

The viscosity of the ink and the surface tension affect the ink transfer and its setting on the printing substrate (Davies & Claypole, 2006; Schaeffer, Fisch & Zettlemoyer, 1963). The lower the viscosity of the ink, the greater the chances that it will flow over the non-porous substrate or penetrate the pores of the porous substrate (Fetsko & Walker, 1955; Walker & Fetsko, 1955; Damroth et al., 1996). The decrease in ink viscosity occurs mainly due to the thinning of the

ink by shear as a consequence of high printing speeds (Zang, 1992), but it can also be the result of an increase in temperature. For example, the authors (Dejidas & Destree, 2005) in their research state that an increase in temperature of 5.5 °C can lead to a decrease in the viscosity of water-based ink by as much as 50%.

(Olsson et al., 2007) noted in their study that lower viscosity inks penetrate better into porous printing substrates, thereby allowing larger amounts of ink to immobilize. As ink separation occurs in ink itself during its mobile phase (transfer phase), the relative ink transfer increases. In addition, the low viscosity of the ink contributes to better spreading and leveling of the ink layer, thus reducing smaller unevenness.

(Walker & Fetsko, 1955) in their study also briefly discussed the effect of vehicle viscosity on ink transfer, stating that lower vehicle viscosity apparently improves ink transfer. However, this observation is not fully covered by the research.

(Taylor & Zettlemyer, 1958) complemented the research conducted by (Walker & Fetsko, 1955) by investigating how ink transfer is affected by changes in its physical and chemical properties. Their research was focused on the mechanism of separation in the wet ink film between the printing plate and the printing substrate at the exit of the printing NIP. Ink separation is accelerated by variations in viscosity within a thin layer of ink. These variations are caused by higher temperatures and/or more intense and faster shear, making the ink cohesion weaker in the area closer to the substrate, thus reducing the amount of transferred ink.

The conclusions of the research conducted by (Beynon, 2007) are interesting because they differ from the conclusions of many other researchers. Namely, by conducting experiments, the author concluded that the decrease in optical density that accompanies the decrease in ink viscosity occurs due to a decrease in pigment concentration and a decrease in ink transfer. However, in the submitted data, it can be seen that there is an increase in ink transfer with a decrease in viscosity. In addition, the author found that there is a strong dependence of viscosity parameters and surface coverage. Beynon states that a decrease in viscosity leads to a reduction in ink flowing in highlights and midtones on porous substrates. The author justified this phenomenon by better hydraulic penetration of ink into the substrate (depth) than lateral expansion. The observed flow of ink in shadow areas was justified through the accumulation of the ink in some areas of the non-printing surfaces.

(Hsu, 1962) states that when the viscosity of the ink is higher, the influence of printing speed and pressure is smaller. He also concluded that higher ink viscosity means a lower level of ink penetration into the substrate, although the porosity of the printing substrate greatly influences this. As for the penetration of ink, he concluded that it grows with the increase of the amount of ink on the printing plate, but to a certain extent, i.e. up until the moment when the substrate becomes saturated with ink.

3 CONCLUSION

The anilox roller or anilox sleeve choice has a significant impact on print quality mainly through the achieved density and tonal value increase. The most important anilox roller parameters are screen ruling, capacity, cell shape, cell depth, cell wall thickness, cell depth to width ratio, angle of the cell walls. On the other hand, the combined influence of the pressure setting and printing speed is the critical point of the flexographic printing process if the aim is to obtain regular halftone dots, avoid the halo effect and control the tonal value increase. All of the aforementioned parameters can yield different print quality results depending on the ink viscosity. Apart from that, ink viscosity can be greatly influenced by the printing speed and temperatures, which are developing mainly on the anilox roller surface.

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4 REFERENCES

Beynon, D. G. (2007). Plate to Substrate Ink Transfer in the Flexographic Printing Process. Ph.D. thesis, Swansea University.

Bohan, M. F. J., Townsend, P., Hamblyn, S. M., Claypole, T. C., Gethin D. T (2003). Evaluation of Pressures in Flexographic Printing. In: Proceedings of the TAGA 55th International Annual Technical Conference, TAGA, 6-9 April 2003, Montreal, Canada. Montreal: The Quebec Institute of Graphic Communications, pp. 311-320.

Boonpravit, W. (2006). A Study of Producing Smoother Gradients in the Flexographic Process on Oriented Polypropylene with UV Ink by Varying

Screening Techniques, Gradient Lengths and the Surrounding. Ph.D. thesis. College of Imaging Arts and Sciences of the Rochester.

Borbély, Á., Szentgyörgyvölgyi, R. (2011). Colorimetric Properties of Flexographic Printed Foils: the Effect of Impression. Óbuda University e-Bulletin. 2(1), 31-36.

Bould, D. C., Claypole, T. C., Bohan, M. F. J. (2003). An experimental investigation into flexographic printing plates. *Journal of Graphic Technology*.

Bould, D. C., Claypole, T. C., Bohan, M. F. J. (2004). An investigation into plate deformation in flexographic printing. *Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers. Part B: Journal of Engineering and Manufacture* [online]. 218, 1499-1511. [Viewed 5 June 2020]. Available from: doi: 10.1243/0954405042418428

Bould, D. C., Claypole, T. C., Bohan, M. F. J., Gethin, D. T. (2004). Deformation of Flexographic Printing Plates. In: *Proceedings of the TAGA 56th Annual Technical Conference, TAGA, 18-21 April 2004, San Antonio, Texas*. Rochester: TAGA, pp. 146-162.

Bould, D. C., Hamblyn, S. M., Gethin, D. T., Claypole, T. C. (2011). Effect of impression pressure and anilox specification on solid and halftone density. *Proceedings of the Institute of Mechanical Engineers Part B: Journal of Engineering Manufacture* [online]. 225(5). 699-709. [Viewed 5 June 2020]. Available from: doi: 10.1177/2041297510394072

Cherry, J. A. (2007). Ink Release Characteristics of Anilox Rolls. Ph.D. thesis, Swansea University.

Damroth, G., DiPiazza, J., Hausman, G., Hines, M., Rivas, M., Rose, B., Shaffer, L., Wald, J., Ziegler, T. (1996). The effect of UV flexo ink viscosity, anilox cell volume, and press speed on printed density and dot gain. In: *Proceedings of the TAGA 48th Annual Technical Conference, TAGA, 30 April 1996, Dallas, Texas*. Rochester: TAGA, pp. 86-101.

Davies, G. R., Claypole, T. C. (2006). Effect of Viscosity on Ink Transfer in Gravure Printing. In: *Proceedings of the 33rd International Research Conference of iarigai, iarigai, September 2006, Leipzig, Germany, Zagreb: Zagreb Acta Graphica Publ.*

De Grâce, J. H., Mangin, P. J. (1983). A Mechanistic Approach to Ink Transfer Part I: - Effect of Substrate Properties and Press Conditions. In: W.H. Banks ed.

17th International Conference of Printing Research Institutes, June 1983, Saltsjöbaden, Sweden, London: Pentech Press, pp. 312-332.

Dejidas, L. and Destree, T. (2005). *Sheetfed Offset Press Operating*. Pittsburgh, Pennsylvania: PIA/GATF Press.

Du, B. (2009). *Dot Gain in the Digital Flexographic Process by Varying Screening Techniques and Pressures*. Xi'an University of Technology.

Dunn, T. (2015). *Manufacturing flexible packaging. Materials, machinery, and techniques*. Waltham: Elsevier.

Fetsko, J. M., Walker, W. C. (1955). Measurement of Ink Transfer in Printing Coated Paper. *American Ink Maker*. 33(11), 38-44/67-69.

FFTA (2014). *Flexography: Principles and practices 6.0*. 6th ed. New York: Foundation of Flexographic Technical Association.

Fouche, L., Blayo, A. (2001). Transfer Characterization of UV Flexo Inks. In: *Proceedings of the TAGA Annual Technical Conference, TAGA, 6-9 May 2001, San Diego, California*. TAGA, pp. 426-443.

FTA (2003). *Flexographic Image Reproduction Specifications and Tolerances (FIRST) Book*. 3rd ed. Ronkonkoma: Flexographic Technical Association.

Hamblyn, A (2015). *Effect of plate characteristics on ink transfer in flexographic printing*. Ph.D. thesis, Swansea University.

Hamblyn, S. M. (2004). *The Role of the Plate in the Ink Transfer Process in Flexographic Printing*. Ph.D. thesis, Swansea University.

Hannah, M. (1951). Contact stress and deformation in a thin elastic layer. *The Quarterly Journal of Mechanics and Applied Mathematics*. 4, 94-105.

Holmvall, M., Uesaka, T. (2008). Print Uniformity of Corrugated Board in Flexo Printing: Effects of Corrugated Board and Halftone Dot Deformations. *Packaging Technology and Science* [online]. 21(7), 385-394. [Viewed 3 July 2020]. Available from: doi: 10.1002/pts.816

Hsu, B. (1962). Some Observations on the Ink-Paper Relationship During Printing. In: W. H. Banks ed. *Advances in Printing Science and Technology vol 2- Problems in High Speed Printing*. New York: Pergamon Press. pp. 1-10.

Izdebska, J. (2016). Flexographic Printing. In: J.E. Izdebska, T. Sabu eds. *Printing on Polymers: Fundamentals and Applications* [online]. Elsevier. pp. 179-197.

[Viewed 10 July 2020]. Available from: doi:10.1016/b978-0-323-37468-2.00011-7.

Johnson, J. (2003). The Influence of Moisture, Temperature, Pressure Pulse and Substrate on Print Quality in Flexographic Printing. Karlstad: Karlstad University Studies.

Johnson, J., Rättö, P., Lestelius, M., Blohm, E. (2004). Measuring the Dynamic Nip Pressure in a Flexographic CI-Printing Press. *Nordic Pulp and Paper Journal*. 19, 84-88.

Johnson, J., Rättö, P., Lestelius, M., Järnström, L. (2003). Dynamic Nip Pressure in a Flexographic CI-Printing Press. In: *Proceedings of the TAGA 55th International Annual Technical Conference, TAGA, 6-9 April 2003, Montreal, Canada*. Montreal: The Quebec Institute of Graphic Communications, pp. 357-374.

Laden, P. (1997). *Chemistry and technology of water-based inks*. London: Chapman & Hall.

Lagerstedt, P., Kolseth, P. (1995). Influence of surface energetics on ink transfer in flexo printing. In: *Advances in printing science and technology: proceedings of the 23rd research conference of IARIGAI, 17-19 September 1995, Paris, France*. pp. 269-299.

Lindholm, G., Gustafsson, M., Girard Leloup, L., Vuillermoz, S. (1996). Ink transfer in flexo evaluated by X-ray fluorescence. In: *Proceedings of the TAGA '96 Conference, TAGA, 28 April – 1 May 1996, Dallas, Texas*. pp. 102-117.

Mirle, S. K. (1989). *Studies on Flexography: Characterization of Surface, Compositional and Mechanical Properties of Photopolymer Plates. Printability Experiments and Mathematical Modelling of Flexographic Printing*. Ph.D. thesis. Lehigh University.

Olsson, R., Yang, L., van Stam, J., Lestelius, M. (2006). Effects of ink setting in flexographic printing: Coating polarity and dot gain. *Nordic Pulp and Paper Research Journal*. 21(5), 569-574.

Olsson, R., Yang, L., van Stam, J., Lestelius, M. (2007). Effects of elevated temperature on flexographic printing. In: *Advances in Printing and Media Technology: proceedings of the 34th International Research Conference of IARIGAI, 9-12 September 2007, Grenoble, France*. pp. 85-93.

Quinn, J. A., Valenzuela, D. P., Micale, F. J., Lavelle, J. S. (1997). Does the Surface Energy of the Plate Affect Ink Transfer?. *CONVERTER e Cartotecnica*. 10, 135-143.

Schaeffer, W. D., Fisch, A. B., Zettlemyer, A. C. (1963). Transfer and Penetration Aspects of Ink Receptivity. *Tappi*. 46(6), 359-375.

Taylor, J. H., Zettlemyer, A. C. (1958). Hypothesis on the Mechanism of Ink Splitting During Printing. *Tappi Journal*. 41(12), 749-757.

Valdec, D., Miljković, P., Čerepinko, D. (2018). The Impact of Top Dot Shapes of the Printing Plate on Dot Formation in Flexography. *Technical Gazette*. 25(2), 596-602.

Valdec, D., Zjakić, I., Milković, M. (2013). The influence of variable parameters of flexographic printing on dot geometry of pre-printed printing substrate. *Tehnički vjesnik*. 20(4), 659-667.

Walker, W. C., Fetsko, J. M. (1955). A Concept of Ink Transfer in Printing. *American Ink Maker*. 33(12), 38-44/69-71.

Zang, Y. H. (1992). Asymmetric splitting and ink transfer: a new ink transfer model. In: *Proceedings of the 6th International Printing and Graphic Arts conference, TAPPI*. Peachtree Corners: TAPPI, pp. 103-112.